

at transplanting and root dipping, and 3) the combined effect of seedling age and seed and seedbed nutrient treatments.

Of the ADT31 seedlings transplanted at 25 DS, those that received 2 kg diammonium phosphate/40 m² in the seedbed yielded 6.1 t/ha (Table 2). Those that were treated with 3% diammonium phosphate solution at seed sprouting yielded 0.5 t/ha more than those that were not. Of the seedlings transplanted at 40 days old, those that received a seedbed application of diammonium phosphate yielded 0.3 t/ha

higher than those that did not; those that were treated with diammonium phosphate at seed sprouting yielded 0.2 t/ha less than those that were not.

The application of diammonium phosphate to the seedbed or to the sprouted seed may be desirable for increasing the yields of 25-day-old seedlings. When the roots of such seedlings were previously dipped in 4% manganese sulfate solution, the yield was significantly higher than that of the control, but almost the same as that of the seedlings whose roots had been dipped in 3% zinc sulfate solution. In

seedlings transplanted at 40 DS, root dipping in zinc sulfate adversely affected grain yield.

The 25-day-old seedlings that received both potassium chloride seed treatment and diammonium phosphate treatment of the sprouted seed yielded the same as the seedlings that received diammonium phosphate seedbed treatment alone (Table 3). The best combination was seed treatment with 1% potassium chloride solution, seedbed manuring with diammonium phosphate, and transplanting at 25 DS. ■

Straw as a source of nutrients for wetland rice

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Rice straw is a natural source of plant nutrients. It contains about 0.6% nitrogen, 0.1% phosphorus, 3% potassium, 8% silicon, and several micronutrients. The common Southeast Asian practice of burning the straw at threshing sites in the field sends up in smoke almost all the nitrogen and renders spotty the distribution of other elements. If the straw is incorporated into the soil, about 30 kg N/ha, 6 kg P/ha, and 150 kg K/ha, and 400 kg Si/ha will be returned to the soil evenly each season. Besides, the added organic matter should encourage nitrogen fixation by anaerobic bacteria. Because no information on the long-term effects of straw on nutrient balance in soils and the growth of rice in the tropics was available, two field experiments on Maahas clay (pH: 6.4, O.M.: 3.3%, total N: 0.130%, exchangeable K: 1.05 meq/100 g, Olsen P: 5.5 ppm) were started in 1972 at IRRI.

In one experiment we compared the long-term effects of four straw management practices — removal, burning in situ, plowing in, and application as compost — on the nutrient content of the soil and growth of wetland rice. The results are in Table 1.

Compared with straw removal, straw

incorporation caused significant increases of 0.47% organic matter, 0.023% nitrogen, 3.9 ppm available phosphorus, and 0.26 meq/100 g of exchangeable potassium. The accumulated nutrients

amounted to 38 kg N, 0.7 kg available P, and 17 kg exchangeable K/ha per season.

In a parallel experiment on Maahas clay, we studied the influence of straw incorporation under four water regimes.

Table 1. Effects of 4 straw treatments on the nutrient status of Maahas clay after the 12th cropping season.^a

Straw treatment	pH	Organic matter (%)	Total N (%)	Olsen P (ppm)	Exchangeable K (meq/100 g)
Removed	6.2 a	3.26 b	.187 b	11.6 c	1.19 c
Burned	6.2 a	3.17 b	.187 b	13.4 bc	1.35 ab
Plowed in	5.9 a	3.13 a	.210 a	15.5 b	1.45 a
Applied as compost	6.2 a	4.01 a	.211 a	27.6 a	1.27 bc

^aIn each column, any two means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 2. Effects of straw incorporation on the nutrient status of Maahas clay under 3 water regimes after the 12th cropping season.

Water regime	Difference between straw and no-straw treatments				
	pH	Organic matter (%)	Total (%)	Olsen p (ppm)	Exchangeable K (meq/100 g)
Dry fallow	-0.3 *	0.38 *	0.021 *	1.8*	0.20*
Dry fallow with msd ^a	-0.2 ns	0.60**	0.020ns	2.3*	0.10ns
Flood fallow	-0.3 *	0.52*	0.029*	1.1ns	0.20 ⊗
Mean	-0.2 *	0.50**	0.023**	1.7**	0.17*

^aMidseason drying. * = significant at the 5% level. ⊗ = nearly significant at the 5% level. ** = significant at the 1% level. ns = nonsignificant.

Table 3. Effects of straw incorporation on the nutrient content of 3 soils and the yield of the 6th rice crop on them.

Soil	Increase due to straw incorporation ^a					Yield (g/drum)	%
	Organic matter (%)	Total N (%)	Olsen P (ppm)	Exchangeable K (meq/100 g)	Yield		
Luisiana clay	0.34**	0.013*	1.0 ns	0.102**	51*	35	
Maahas clay	0.08 ns	0.008 ns	0.7 ns	0.183**	40 ns	29	
Pila clay loam	0.25 *	0.023**	3.0**	0.128**	50*	45	
Mean	0.22 **	0.015**	1.6*	0.138**	47*	36	

^aSignificant at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels. ns = nonsignificant.

The results are in Table 2.

Nutrient accumulation due to straw incorporation, averaged for the three water regimes, was as follows:

Nutrient	kg/ha per season
Total N	38
Available P	3
Exchangeable K	11

In 2 parallel 6-year-long field experiments, incorporation of straw produced in situ gave the identical value of 38 kg/ha per season for nitrogen added. Although the content of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium increased, yield was low with or without straw incorporation and the benefit of straw incorporation small because of zinc

deficiency and boron toxicity induced by bad irrigation water.

To ascertain whether comparable amounts of nutrients were added in other soils, the effect of straw incorporation at 5 t/ha on the nutrient status of three soils was studied outdoors in 200-liter steel drums. The soils were Luisiana clay (pH: 6.7, total N: 0.154%), Maahas clay (pH: 7.1, total N: 0.130%), and Pila clay loam (pH: 7.7, total N: 0.109%).

Nitrogen accretion varied with the soil: it was highest in Pila clay loam and least in Maahas clay. In all three soils straw incorporation significantly increased grain yield (Table 3). The increase in nutrient content on a hectare basis was as follows:

Clay	Increase (kg/ha per season)		
	Total N	Available P	Exchangeable K
Luisiana clay	43	0.3	13
Maahas clay	26	0.2	24
Pila clay loam	77	1.0	17
Mean	49	0.5	18

Incorporation of straw brought about an increase of 38 kg nitrogen and about 14 kg/ha per season of exchangeable potassium in two field experiments on Maahas clay. The corresponding increases averaged for three soils in a drum study were 49 kg N and 18 kg K.

Incorporating straw increases the natural supply of nutrients in wetland rice soils. ■

Efficient use of fertilizer nitrogen in wetland rice under poor water management

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A split application of nitrogen sometimes increases fertilizer efficiency and yields of wetland rice more than does a single basal application. But the efficiency of split-applied nitrogen depends on water management. Water-management constraints in farmers' fields include field-to-field irrigation, lack of drainage facilities, and over irrigation prompted by irregular water supply. Therefore the practice of split nitrogen application was evaluated under both controlled and uncontrolled irrigation in the 1978 wet season in five villages under the Operational Research Project, Miryalguda, Andhra Pradesh. The soil was a red sandy loam with pH 7.8-8.0 and 0.52-0.86% organic matter. Controlled irrigation (CI) involved submergence at 2- to 5-cm level through separate channels, drainage before topdressing of nitrogen, and reflooding. Uncontrolled irrigation (UI) practices were the farmers' normal heavy application of irrigation water (submergence level varying from 5 to 20 cm), field-to-field irrigation, and topdressing of nitrogen on

Effect of water management on grain yield and efficiency of urea-nitrogen applied at 100 kg N/ha. Mean of 5 experimental sites in a farmer's field. Andhra Pradesh, India, 1978 wet season.^a

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		Yield response (kg grain/kg fertilizer N)		Recovery of fertilizer N in grain + straw (%) (Differential method)	
	CI ^b	UI ^b	CI	UI	CI	UI
Control, no N	3.6	3.1	—	—	—	—
Urea, 3 splits	6.0	4.4	23.2	13.4	40.3	21.9
NC-urea, 3 splits	6.0	4.9	23.0	18.2	29.4	24.7
NC-urea, all basal	6.7	5.6	30.7	25.1	65.9	46.5
LSD (0.05)	0.66		7.80		9.08	
CV (%)	10.00		16.50		18.05	

^a NC-urea = urea blended with neem cake (residue of *Azadirachta indica* seed after oil extraction) at 30% by weight of urea using coal tar solution. Split application = 25% basal with incorporation, 50% topdressed at active tillering stage and 25% at panicle initiation.

^b CI = controlled irrigation, UI = uncontrolled irrigation.

floodwater with no previous drainage.

All treatments required careful water management for best results (see table).

Yields decreased about 26% when split application of ordinary urea was associated with the farmers' poor management of irrigation water.

Despite poor water management, basal application of neem cake-blended urea gave yields, yield responses, and crop recovery of added nitrogen equal to those of split application of ordinary urea under ideal conditions. ■

Effect of seedling age and number per hill on grain yield of rice varieties

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Seedlings of rice varieties Pusa 2-21 and Jaya were transplanted at 20, 40, and 60 days after seeding to study the extent of yield reduction when transplanting

is delayed. To compensate for yield reduction 2, 4, or 6 seedlings/hill were transplanted. The experiment used a randomized block design with four replications. The crop was sown in wet nursery beds at the Crop Research Center, Pantnagar on 16 June in the 1977-78 wet season.

When older seedlings of short-duration Pusa 2-21 were transplanted, yield reduction was consistent regardless of